

FORMALDEHYDE FORMATION IN THE PHOTO-OXIDATION OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS AND THE FORMALDEHYDE THEORY OF CARBON ASSIMILATION.

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It has been observed that formaldehyde is produced during the photo-oxidation of organic compounds such as, glycine, citric acid, acetic acid, oxalic acid, canesugar etc.

On the basis of the amount of formaldehyde formed during photo-oxidation, all the organic substances investigated by the authors have been divided into three groups :—

(a) Formaldehyde obtained as a direct product of photo-oxidation such as, glycine, acetic acid, methyl violet etc .

(b) Formaldehyde obtained may be partly due to the direct photo-oxidation of the substance and partly due to its photosynthesis from carbon dioxide generated during oxidation.

(c) Formaldehyde detected may be due to its photosynthesis from energy-rich carbon dioxide produced during photo-oxidation.

The production of formaldehyde is not only limited to substances of biochemical origin as observed by Moore, Wager etc, but it can be detected during the photo-oxidation of any organic substances provided it can be oxidised to carbon dioxide and water in light.

It is easier to obtain formaldehyde from carbon dioxide generated during the photo-oxidation from organic compounds than from potassium bicarbonate solutions or carbon dioxide solution because the former is associated with energy evolved during oxidation.

The energy produced during respiration is concluded to supply a part of the energy need for photosynthesis.

Besides light, carbon dioxide, moisture and chlorophyll, energy from respiration seems also necessary for photosynthesis.

Numerous attempts have been made to imitate *in vitro* the phenomenon of photosynthesis in plants by exposing solutions of carbonic acid or bicarbonate with or without photocatalysts to different radiations. In the natural process, however, the carbon assimilation, which is a highly endothermal reaction

is influenced not only by the light radiations but is also aided by the plant respiration.

It is well known that in the process of germination of seeds, there is considerable loss of energy-rich material by oxidation and this phenomenon supplies the major portion of the energy required for the seedling. It appears that under natural conditions, the endothermal reaction involved

in formaldehyde or glucose formation in plants takes place by absorption of solar radiations and by the partial utilisation of the energy of respiration. Hence, it seems likely that it is easier to obtain formaldehyde or any other energy-rich compound from carbonic acid and bicarbonate solutions on exposure to light when a suitable exothermal reaction is also taking place in the system along with the photosynthetic reaction.

The researches of Palit and Dhar (*cf.* Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry", 1932) show that sugars and other energy materials are oxidised by air when their solutions or suspensions are exposed to light and air. The carbonic acid formed in these oxidations not only receives the light radiations but is also supplied with the energy liberated in the oxidations of the sugars and other carbonaceous compounds. Hence, the photoformation of formaldehyde is likely to be easier in such cases, where two energy sources are available than in those in which carbonic acid or bicarbonate solutions are exposed to light alone. Moreover, it has been discovered in this laboratory that sunlight or artificial light markedly increases nitrogen fixation ($N_2 + O_2 + 43.2 \text{ K.Cal} = 2NO$) in soils mixed with energy materials. In this case, the endothermal reaction involved in nitrogen fixation is not only aided by the energy of the carbohydrate oxidation ($C_6H_{12}O_6 + 6O_2 = 6CO_2 + 6H_2O + 676 \text{ K.Cal}$) but is also accelerated by the absorption of light radiations, which are actually utilised in bringing about more nitrogen fixation. The nitrogen fixation in light, where both the oxidation energy and the radiation energy are utilised, is nearly twice that of the fixation in the dark, when only the energy of the oxidation is available for the endothermal reaction involved in nitrogen fixation.

We have carried on a systematic work on the photoformation of formaldehyde by the photo-oxidation of different organic substances for several years and most of our results are recorded in this paper, which is a continuation of a previous publication (Dhar and Atma Ram, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 287) in which a few observations were reported.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Merck's or Kahlbaum's samples of the organic substances were used and were further purified by crystallisation. Dilute solutions usually $M/100$ or $M/1000$ in the case of the dyes were exposed to bright sunshine in Jena flasks, well stoppered and kept in a water-bath at a constant temperature. After an exposure of six hours or more, an aliquot part from the exposed solutions was distilled and the presence of formaldehyde was detected by Schryver's test. When it was established that formaldehyde

is actually produced during the photo-oxidation of a certain substance, it was necessary to estimate this amount.

The estimation of very small quantities of formaldehyde is difficult. The methods for its estimation already in vogue, such as, the iodometric and the urotropin method were both tried with unsatisfactory results. We have, therefore, applied Schryver's test for a colorimetric estimation of formaldehyde, which is carried on as follows. It may be pointed out here that it is possible to detect formaldehyde when present even in such small amounts as 0.000015 g. in 100 c. c. provided all the precautions are taken.

Estimation of Formaldehyde by the Colorimetric Method.

All the reagents (phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and potassium ferricyanide) used in the test should be prepared fresh. A standard solution of formaldehyde was prepared by diluting solution whose strength had already been determined by the iodometric method. 5 C. c. of the solution to be estimated were taken in a clear test tube and 5 c.c. of the standard solution in another one, and the reagents added in the proper order (phenylhydrazine, ferricyanide and hydrochloric acid). When the colour developed, which usually takes about five minutes, the contents of the two tubes were poured into those of the colorimeter, and the colours of the two tubes matched.

Group I.

Formaldehyde produced as a direct product of photo-oxidation.

TABLE I.

50 C°c. solutions in water exposed at 30° for 8 hours in open beakers.

Acids.			
Substances exposed.	Amount of H·CHO produced per 100 c.c. soln.	Substances exposed.	Amount of 4 CHO produced per 100 c.c. soln.
2 <i>N</i> -Acetic acid	0.0011 g.	<i>N</i> /5-Malic acid	0.001 g.
<i>N</i> /5-Citric acid	0.0012	<i>N</i> /5-Monochloroacetic acid	0.00095
<i>N</i> /5-Lactic acid	0.0009	<i>N</i> /100-Glycine	0.0013
Dyes.			
0.02%-Malachite green	0.00096	0.02%-Gentian violet	0.00085
0.02%-Methylene blue	0.00075	0.02%-Auramine	0.0007
0.02%-Methyl violet	0.0012	0.02%-Victoria blue	0.00091
0.02%-Crystal violet	0.0009	0.02%-Acridine orange	0.00072
Miscellaneous.			
1%-Guaiacol	0.0011	2%-Glycol	0.00086
2%-Glycerol	0.0009	Suspension containing 0.02 g. chlorophyll	0.00096

Group II.

TABLE II.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Substance exposed.	Amount of H·CHO formed in g. per 100 c. c. of the soln.	Substance exposed.	Amount of H·CHO formed in g. per 100 c.c. of the soln.
N/5-Tartaric acid	0·0002	0·02% Gallomine blue	0·00045
N/1-Propionic acid	0·00021	0·02% Aurine	0·00025
N/1-Butyric acid	0·00016	1% Galactose	0·00036
N/5-Pyruvic acid	0·00034	1% fructose (50 c.c.)	0·00052
0·02%-Phloxine	0·00041		

Group III.

Formaldehyde produced as a result of its photosynthesis from the carbon dioxide produced during the photo-oxidation.

TABLE III.

Conditions same as in Table I.

Substance exposed.	Amount of H·CHO formed in g. per 100 c. c. of the soln.	Substance exposed.	Amount of H·CHO formed in g. per 100 c.c. of the soln.
Carbohydrates.			
1% Cane sugar	0·00005	1% Mannitol	0·000055
Glucose	0·000045	Sorbitol	0·00003
Arabinose	0·00004	Starch	0·00003
		Inulin	0·000035
Acids			
N/5-Oxalic acid	0·000065	N/5-glutaric acid	0·00004
Malonic acid	0·000052	adepic acid	0·000035
Succinic acid	0·00005		

TABLE III. (contd).

Amino-acids.			
<i>N</i> /50-Alanine (a)	0'00007	<i>N</i> /50-Cystein	0'00006
Phenylalanine	0'00004	Cysteine	0'00009
Leucine	0'000055	Tryptophau	0'000085
Valine	0'00004	Arginine	0'00015
Lysine	0'000048	Tyrosine (a)	0'000074
Aspartic acid	0'000074	Hippuric acid	0'000042
Glutamic acid	0'000067	Histidine	0'00004
Asparagine	0'000045	Uric acid	0'00003
Salts and Esters.			
<i>N</i> /1-Sodium acetate	0'000093	<i>N</i> /100-Sodium oleate	0'000098
Sodium formate	0'000075	Sodium stearate	0'000084
Sodium propionate	0'000067	Sodium palmitate	0'000078
Sodium butyrate	0'000054	1%-Ethyl acetate	0'000055
Sodium oxalate	0'000063		
Dyes.			
0'02%-Congo red	0'00003	0'02%-Methyl red	0'00004
Safranine	0'000056	Naphthachrome	0'000013
Acridine yellow	0'00006	Pinaverdol	0'00003
Orthochrome	0'00015	Benzopurpurin	0'00004
Pinachrome	0'00009	Chrysophenine	0'000012
Pinaflavol	0'0001	Brilliant green	0'00007
Pinacyanole	0'00008	Neutral red	0'0001
Rhodamin	0'00006	Aniline orange	0'00008
Eosin	0'000012	Bixin	0'00011
		Aniline green	0'00008
Miscellaneous.			
0'3%-Gelatine	0'000065	Dilute suspension of ergosterol	0'000065
0'5%-Creatinine	0'00007	Suspension of cholesterol	0'000075
0'5%-Creatin	0'000054		

Oxygen is necessary for the Production of Formaldehyde from Organic Substances in Light.

In a previous communication (Dhar and Atma Ram, *loc. cit.*) the production of formaldehyde from substances of the first group has been explained as a direct product of photo-oxidation. If that is so, oxygen should be necessary in order that any formaldehyde may be formed from glycine, citric acid etc. Experiments were carried out to this point, by exposing dilute solutions of glycine and citric acid to sunlight in presence of oxygen and also in atmospheres of nitrogen, hydrogen, carbon dioxide etc. The following table contains some of the results.

TABLE IV.

50 C. c. of solution exposed in soft glass bulbs for 8 hours at 30°.

Gas with which the soln. has been saturated.	Amount of H.CHO formed per 100 c.c. of the soln.	
	N/50-Glycine.	N/5-Citric acid.
Oxygen	0'0011 g.	0'0012 g.
Nitrogen	0'00005	0'000045
Carbon dioxide	0'000065	0'00007
Hydrogen	0'00003	0'00003

In all cases conductivity water saturated with the different gases was also exposed in glass bulbs and tested with the exposed solutions. The absence of formaldehyde in all these bulbs and also in the dark, points out that formaldehyde in the above experiments is not obtained from impurities, but is produced from the organic substance undergoing photo-oxidation.

From these results it will be seen that the production of formaldehyde from glycine or citric acid involves a chemical change in which oxygen plays a very important part. It appears that the generation of formaldehyde from substances of the first group is a case of photo-oxidation and not of photodecomposition, *i. e.*, light and air or oxygen are both necessary for this reaction.

Ratio of the Number of Molecules of the Organic Substances oxidised to those of Formaldehyde formed.

In order to throw light on the problem whether formaldehyde obtained from the photo-oxidation of the substances of the first group is a direct

product of the photo-oxidation, experiments were carried on for determining the ratio of the number of molecules of the organic substances oxidised to those of formaldehyde formed. We have advanced the view that the important chemical change involved in the photo-oxidation of glycine can be represented as follows :—

From this equation, it is evident that a molecule of glycine on its photo-oxidation gives rise to one molecule each of ammonia and formaldehyde. If the amount of glycine oxidised and that of formaldehyde formed can be estimated, this ratio can be easily calculated. The amount of amino-acid oxidised by air in light has been determined by treating it before and after the experiment with potassium permanganate and sodium carbonate and estimating the amount of ammonia produced. From the difference the amount of amino-acid oxidised by air in light can be calculated.

As a result of their researches on the photo-decomposition of formaldehyde, Norrish and Kirkbridge (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1518) have observed that the main products of decomposition are carbon monoxide and hydrogen. It seems likely that formaldehyde produced in our oxidation experiments may be partially lost in this way. Thus in calculating the ratio, a correction has to be made for the amount of formaldehyde lost which was determined by a separate experiment.

The following results have been obtained on the ratio: $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}/\text{HCHO}$, making an allowance for the amount of formaldehyde decomposed. The amounts of amino-acids oxidised and the formaldehyde formed, have been expressed in g. moles.

TABLE V.

M/100-Solution (50 c.c.) exposed to sunlight for 8 hours at 30°.

	Amino-acid oxidised in g. moles/100 c.c.	HCHO de- tected in g. moles/100 c.c.	HCHO that would have been detected without decomp.	Ratio with decompo- sition.	Ratio without decomposi- tion.
I.	0'00002	0'000016	0'0000185	1'1	1'2
II.	0'000019	0'000017	0'0000175	1'06	1'3
III.	0'000021	0'000017	0'0000185	1'14	1'24

From the foregoing results it appears that formaldehyde produced during the photo-oxidation of glycine is a direct product of the photo-oxidation reaction, as the ratio of the amino-acid oxidised to the formaldehyde formed is nearly unity.

Influence of the Wave-length of the Light on the Photoformation of Formaldehyde from Substances of the First Group.

In order to study the influence of different wave-lengths of light on these reactions, comparative experiments were performed by exposing dilute solutions of glycine, citric acid, malic acid etc., in quartz flasks. It has generally been found that the yield of formaldehyde from these substances is increased in ultraviolet light. The following table contains some of the results.

TABLE VI.

50 C. c. of the solution exposed for 6 hours at 30°.

Substance exposed.	Amount of formaldehyde per 100 c.c.	
	Total light from 1000 watt gas filled tung- sten lamp.	mercury vapour lamp.
N/100 Glycine	0'00025 g.	0'00045 g.
N/10-Citric acid	0'00035	0'0006
N/10-Malic acid	0'0002	0'00046

It is seen, therefore, that ultraviolet light has a greater effect on the yield of formaldehyde from glycine, citric acid etc., than the total light from a gasfilled tungsten filament lamp.

Temperature Coefficient of the Photoformation of Formaldehyde from Substances of the First Group.

During recent years, a systematic study of the influence of temperature on photochemical reactions has been helpful in the elucidation of the mechanism of such processes. With this object in view, an attempt was made to study the temperature coefficients of these reactions. It may be stated that in this investigation the temperature coefficient means the ratio of the yields of formaldehyde at two different temperatures. This is due to the fact that the velocity of the photo-oxidation is too slow for the measurement of the actual velocity coefficient.

FORMALDEHYDE FORMATION IN THE PHOTO-OXIDATION, ETC. 329

N/50. solution of glycine and 0.01% solution of methyl violet were exposed in 500 c. c. Jena glass flasks well stoppered and kept at different temperatures. In the following tables some of the results have been summarised.

TABLE VII.

N/50-Solution glycine (50 c.c.) exposed for 6 hours.

Temp.	Amount of HCHO. formed per 100 c.c.	Temp. coeff.
20°	0.00028 g.	1.66
30°	0.0003 .	1.4
40°	0.00042	1.25
50°	0.00052	1.06
60°	0.00055	

TABLE VIII.

Methyl violet (0.01%).

Temp.	Amount of HCHO formed per 100 c.c.	Amount of dye decomposed per 100 c.c.	Temp. coeff.
30°	0.0000079 g. moles.	0.0000027 g. moles.	1.2
40°	0.0000095	0.0000035	1.1
50°	0.0000105	0.0000043	

An examination of these results, shows that the temperature coefficient of the photoformation of formaldehyde from substances of the first group is somewhat more than unity and goes on decreasing as the temperature rises. These are cases of photo-oxidations, since no formaldehyde is produced in the dark.

It has already been pointed out that the origin of formaldehyde, detected during the photo-oxidation of substances like oxalic acid, α -alanine, cane sugar etc., is its photosynthesis from carbon dioxide and water, which are produced during the photo-oxidation of organic compounds. From comparative experiments it has been found that a solution of α -alanine is oxidised to a greater extent than a solution of glycine of the same concentration, although the amount of formaldehyde formed from the latter is about twenty times greater than that obtained from α -alanine. This is probably

due to the fact that formaldehyde is obtained from glycine as a direct product of photo-oxidation of the latter, whilst from α -alanine it is produced as a result of its photosynthesis from the energy-rich carbon dioxide and water generated during photo-oxidation. In order to understand the mechanism of the formation of formaldehyde from substances of the third group, comparative experiments on the ratio of the amount of the substance oxidised to that of formaldehyde formed have been carried out. Since oxalic, malonic, succinic acids, etc. can be easily estimated by titrating against a standard baryta solution in the usual manner by using phenolphthalein as an indicator, it was considered advisable to study the photo-oxidation of these acids. Moreover, these experiments have also been carried out with amino-acids like α -alanine, valine, leucine, aspartic acid etc.

Experimental Determination of the Ratio of the Amount of Organic Substance Photo-oxidised to the Amount of Formaldehyde formed from Substances of the Third Group.

The amount of formaldehyde produced from oxalic acid, α -alanine etc. being small, it is necessary that the amount of formaldehyde decomposed on exposure to light should be accounted for in determining the ratio of the acid decomposed to formaldehyde formed.

Standard solutions of the three acids were exposed in quartz flasks of the same capacity, well fitted with stoppers. The amount of the acid oxidised was estimated by titrating it against a standard baryta solution in the usual manner with phenolphthalein as an indicator, before and after the exposure. The amount of formaldehyde was determined by the colorimetric method. The amount of the substances oxidised and the formaldehyde formed have been expressed in g. moles in these tables.

TABLE IX.

50 C.c. of $N/5$ -solution exposed for 8 hours at 30° .

Substance exposed.	Amount of H·CHO formed per 100 c.c.	Amount of the acid oxidised.		Ratio Acid oxidised. H·CHO
Oxalic acid	0·000033 g. moles	0·00109 g. moles	5·4%	330
Malonic	0·000027	0·00033	1·6	122
Succinic	0·000023	0·0002	1·0	89
Glutaric	0·000018	0·00015	0·75	83

FORMALDEHYDE FORMATION IN THE PHOTO-OXIDATION, ETC. 331

It will be seen from these observations, that as many as 330 molecules of oxalic acid are oxidised per molecule of formaldehyde formed. Moreover, in the homologous series of the dicarboxylic acids, the amount of formaldehyde produced from a solution of oxalic acid is greatest and goes on decreasing as the molecular weight of the homologue increases. But the percentage of acid oxidised to that of formaldehyde formed goes on decreasing with increasing molecular weights.

TABLE X.

Substance exposed.	Amount of H·CHO formed per 100 c.c.	Amount of the substance oxidised per 100 c.c.		Ratio Substance oxidised. H·CHO
Cane sugar	0·0000017 g. moles	0·00015 g. moles	1·5%	88
Glucose	0·0000017	0·00016	1·6	94
α-Alanine	0·0000018	0·00021	2·1	117
Aspartic acid	0·0000015	0·00018	1·8	120

These results lend support to the view that formaldehyde produced from substances of the third group owes its origin to photosynthesis from carbon dioxide and water produced during photo-oxidation, as the ratio of the amount of substance oxidised to the amount of formaldehyde formed is much higher than unity as obtained with substances of the first group.

Comparative Experiments on the Ratio of the Amount of Substance oxidised to that of Formaldehyde formed from Substances of Different Groups.

It has been stated before that the production of formaldehyde from substance of the third group is due to its photosynthesis from the energy-rich carbon dioxide generated during photo-oxidation. If that is true, the ratio of the amount of the substance oxidised to amount of formaldehyde formed, should be greater with substances of the third group than with those of the first group, where it is obtained as a direct product of the photo-oxidation. The following experiments were carried on by exposing aqueous solutions of different substances having the same concentration.

TABLE XI.

M/100 solution (50 c.c.) exposed in quartz flasks for 8 hours at 30°.

Group No.	Substance.	Amount of H·CHO formed per 100 c.c.	Amount of the acid oxidised per 100 c.c.	Ratio.
I	Glycine	0·00003 g. moles	0·000033 g. moles	1·1
II	α -Alanine	0·000017	0·00012	7·1
III	Valine	0·000012	0·000071	5·9

It is evident from the results that the ratio of the amount of substance oxidised to that of formaldehyde formed is greater with the third group of substances than with those of the first group. The amount of formaldehyde produced from a substance of the third group is much less than that obtained from a substance having the same chemical character but belonging to the first group. On the other hand, the percentage amount of the substance oxidised of the third group is much greater than that of a compound belonging to the first group.

This observation is rather striking and appears to lead to the conclusion that the generation of formaldehyde from substances of the third group cannot be a case of direct photo-oxidation, since it is not likely that the direct formation of a molecule of formaldehyde is caused by the oxidation of three hundred molecules of oxalic acid or sugar. The mechanism of the photoformation of formaldehyde from oxalic acid, cane sugar etc. seems to be its photosynthesis from the energy-rich carbon dioxide which is a product of photo-oxidation.

Temperature Coefficient of Photosynthesis of Formaldehyde from Energy-rich Carbon Dioxide produced during Photo-oxidation of Organic Substances.

In preceding pages, it has been pointed out that the temperature coefficient of photoformation of formaldehyde from substances of the first group goes on decreasing as the temperature increases and tends to be unity at about 60°. For instance, in the case of glycine the temperature coefficient between 10° and 20° is 1·8 and between 50°-60° is 1·06. Since almost all the oxidation reactions are accelerated by increase of temperature, it is expected that the production of formaldehyde from substances of the third group may also be increased with temperature, if it is a case of direct photo-oxidation. Hence an investigation of the temperature coefficient of these

reactions may also throw light on the generation of formaldehyde in the third group of substances. In order to test this point, a systematic study of the temperature coefficient of these reactions was undertaken.

Dilute solutions of oxalic acid, malonic acid, orthochrome etc. were exposed in thin layers in petri dishes and covered by quartz covers, thereby allowing all the light to fall on the exposed solutions and avoiding the dust. Since it is necessary to show that no formaldehyde is obtained in these experiments due to contamination, blank experiments were carried on. Solutions of substances under investigation were kept in shade in the same locality contained in similar vessels. In a clean dish some distilled water was exposed side by side. The temperature of the exposed solutions was maintained within 1°.

TABLE XII.

Oxalic acid.

N/5-Solution (50 c. c.) exposed in petri dishes covered with quartz cover for 8 hours.

Temp.	Amount of the		Temp. coeff. with regard to	
	acid oxidised per 100 c.c.	H·CHO formed per 100 c. c.	acid oxidised.	H·CHO formed.
10°	0'0003 g. moles	0'000001 g. moles	1'0	1'9
20°	0'0006	0'0000019	1'5	1'5
30°	0'0009	0'000003	1'3	0'76
40°	0'00115	0'0000023	1'17	0'6
50°	0'00133	0'0000014		

These results are interesting from the view-point of the mechanism of the photoformation of formaldehyde from substances like oxalic acid. On an examination of columns 4 and 5, it will be seen that up to 30° the temperature coefficient of the reaction is more than unity with regard to formaldehyde formation as well as acid oxidised. On the other hand, a peculiar behaviour is observed if these experiments are carried on at temperatures above 30°. The value of the temperature coefficient with regard to formaldehyde formation becomes less than unity, while with regard to acid decomposition it still remains more than unity,

TABLE XIII.

Orthochrome.

0.02% Solution (50 c. c.) exposed in petri dishes covered with quartz covers for 8 hours.

Temp.	Amount of the		Temp. coefficient with regard to	
	HCHO formed per 100 c. c.	dye decomposed per 100 c. c.	HCHO formation.	dye decomposition.
10°	0.000007 g. moles	0.000028 g moles	2.1	2.2
20°	0.000015	0.00006	1.6	1.7
30°	0.000025	0.0001	0.6	1.3
40°	0.000015	0.00013	0.53	1.25
50°	0.000008	0.00015		

These results are also in agreement with those obtained with oxalic acid. The yield of formaldehyde goes on increasing upto 30° but becomes less as the temperature is raised higher than 30°. It seems that this influence of temperature on the photoformation of formaldehyde from oxalic acid, orthochrome etc. is a general characteristic of the third group of compounds.

Comparison of Temperature Coefficient of the Oxidation of Substances of the Groups I and III.

In the following tables temperature coefficients of the two classes have been compared taking citric acid, oxalic acid, methyl violet and orthochrome as typical examples.

TABLE XIV.

Acids.

Temp. limit.	Temperature coefficient with regard to			
	formaldehyde formation.		acid decomposition.	
	Citric acid.	Oxalic acid.	Citric acid	Oxalic acid.
20-30°	1.7	1.5	1.77	1.5
30-40°	1.49	0.76	1.5	1.3
40-50°	1.18	0.6	1.3	1.17

TABLE XV

Dyestuffs.

Temp limit.	Temperature coefficient with regard to			
	formaldehyde formation		the oxidation of the dye.	
	Methyl violet	Ortho- chrome.	Methyl violet.	Ortho- chrome.
20-30°	1.5	1.6	1.56	1.7
30-40°	1.2	0.6	1.3	1.4
40-50°	1.1	0.53	1.16	1.15

The bearing of these results on the mechanism of the two types of reactions is important. It appears that there is a fundamental difference in the mode of formation of formaldehyde from substances of the first group (citric acid and methyl violet) and the third group (oxalic acid and orthochrome). The temperature coefficient for the first group is more than unity at lower temperatures and tends to unity at higher temperature intervals both with regard to acid and dye decomposition and the formation of formaldehyde.

The effect of temperature on substances of the third group is similar to that on those of the first group, only when the temperature coefficient is calculated with regard to the oxidation of the substance. On the other hand, if it is calculated with regard to photoformation of formaldehyde, the values remain more than unity up to 30°, but decrease rapidly at higher temperatures. The temperature coefficient for substances of the first group, both with regard to formaldehyde formation and the substance oxidised, happens to be of the same order, because here it is formed as a direct product of photo-oxidation. It may seem that these observations suggest that the production of formaldehyde from oxalic acid, orthochrome or in general from those of the third group involves two stages.

(i) Photo-oxidation of the organic substance and consequent production of energy-rich carbon dioxide.

(ii) Photosynthesis of formaldehyde from energy-rich carbon dioxide and water so produced.

Low yields of formaldehyde at high temperatures may be due to its loss on account of its photodecomposition, which is more prominent at high temperatures; that is why there is difference between the values of temperature coefficient with the two methods of calculation.

It will be interesting to note here that the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis as observed in plants is less than unity above 30°.

Relation between the Amount of Energy produced during Photo-oxidation of an Organic Substance and the Amount of Formaldehyde formed Photosynthetically.

It is well known that the amount of heat generated per gramme of fat oxidised is 9 calories, whilst with both proteins and carbohydrates it is about 4.1 calories per gramme. In order to find out whether there is any relation between the amount of energy generated in the oxidation of different energy materials and that of formaldehyde photosynthesised during photo-oxidation of an organic substance, we have carried on comparative experiments on the photoformation of formaldehyde not only from the oxidation of organic compounds but have also compared the amount of former obtained by exposing solution of potassium bicarbonate to sunlight. In the following table some of these results have been summarised.

TABLE XVI.

Strength of the solutions exposed = $M/100$ (organic compounds). Strength of the potassium bicarbonate solution = $M/5$. Volume of the solutions exposed = 50 c.c. Containers, quartz flasks. Exposure = 7 hours.

System exposed.	Amount of the substance decomposed or oxidised per 100 c.c.	% of the substance oxidised or decomposed.	Amount of H·CHO formed per 100 c.c.	Ratio of the amount of substance oxidised to that of H·CHO.
KHCO ₃	0.0098 g. mole	49	0.000001 g. mol.	9800
Sodium oleate	0.00011	1.1	0.0000037	29.9
Sodium palmitate	0.000091	0.9	0.000003	30.3
Sodium stearate	0.000082	0.82	0.0000023	36
Cane sugar	0.00015	1.5	0.0000018	83
Glucose	0.00016	1.6	0.0000017	94
α-Alanine	0.00021	2.1	0.0000018	117
Aspartic acid	0.00018	1.8	0.0000015	120

These results are interesting because they show that the amount of formaldehyde formed by exposing potassium bicarbonate solutions to sunlight in quartz vessels is much smaller than that photosynthesised during photo-oxidation of organic substances. Moreover, when we compared the amount

of formaldehyde formed with that of bicarbonate decomposed or the organic substance oxidised, there is a great divergence. The ratio is much greater with the bicarbonates in comparison with the organic compounds. In other words, it is much easier to obtain formaldehyde from carbonic acid generated during the photo-oxidation of an organic compound than from that produced in the decomposition of potassium bicarbonate solutions exposed to light. This is certainly due to the fact that the oxidation of organic matter in air and light generates energy and this is utilised in the photosynthesis of formaldehyde. These observations also show that the amount of formaldehyde obtained is greatest with those substances which generate the maximum amount of energy on their oxidation, *i.e.*, the photoformation of formaldehyde is greater with sodium stearate than with the carbohydrates and amino-acids under identical conditions. It appears that the amount of formaldehyde formed in the photo-oxidation of substances of the third group is directly connected with the energy of oxidation, which is actually utilised in this process along with the radiation energy.

It is concluded, therefore, that the energy generated during oxidation supplies a part of the energy needed for the photosynthesis of formaldehyde. These reactions in which both radiation energy and energy derived from oxidation are utilised in the production of energy-rich compounds appear to be of the same type as in photosynthesis in plants where both the energy of respiration and radiation energy are used up in the synthesis of carbohydrates and other energy materials.

D I S C U S S I O

In the preceding pages, it has been shown that formaldehyde can be obtained by exposing aqueous solutions and suspensions of organic substances to light and air. Though the production of formaldehyde from substances of biochemical origin, when their solutions are exposed to light, has been reported by many observers, the origin of its formation has not yet been explained satisfactorily. We have made the interesting observation that the generation of formaldehyde is not only limited to substances of a biochemical nature, but almost any organic substance can produce it when exposed to light and air provided it can undergo photo-oxidation.

Why is it that formaldehyde is produced during the photo-oxidation of organic substances? It may not be obtained as a direct product of oxidation from all organic compounds. It may be so only in a few cases as in the compounds of the first group.

It seems that the first stage in carbon assimilation taking place *in vitro* and possibly *in vivo* is the photolysis of water molecules into H and OH. Based on this view, we have explained the photoformation of formaldehyde from substances of the third group in the following way

The energy required for this operation is supplied by the solar radiations as well as the energy obtained from the oxidation of the organic substances. This energy (112 K.Cal) corresponds to radiations of wave-length 2552 Å.

Franck (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 536) has postulated that complete light absorption by molecules is associated with their breaking up into atoms. Henri ("Struktur des Molekules", Chapter V, 1925) has observed that increase of temperature causes the light absorption by molecules to begin at longer wave-lengths. Dhar and Bhattacharya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 33) have shown that in general an increase in the light absorption by a molecule is associated with its increased chemical reactivity and weakening of the binding forces of the molecules. Hence when a molecule becomes more reactive, it is likely to absorb light more markedly than otherwise.

So far weakening of the binding forces of a molecule and its increased light absorption have been observed under the influence of physical agencies like radiation or increase of temperature, but the recent researches carried on in these laboratories, have shown for the first time that chemical agencies can also cause weakening of the binding forces followed by increased light absorption by reacting molecules. Thus in the presence of reducing agents like hydrogen, oxalic acid, oxalates, ferrous sulphate etc., the light absorption and reactivity of the halogen molecules are appreciably increased. It has also been observed that there is more absorption of light by solutions of glycine, acetic acid etc., in presence of oxygen than in its absence.

The increased absorption of light by glycine in presence of oxygen seems to be due to the activation of dissolved oxygen molecules by the presence of those of glycine or acetic acid. It appears very likely, therefore, that in presence of glycine or acetic acid, the reactivity of oxygen will be increased and hence the photo-oxidation of organic substances like glycine and acetic acid by oxygen is possible even in sunlight.

In the second group, the amount of formaldehyde formed during the photo-oxidation is less than that produced in the first class and more than that obtained with the third class of substances. It is difficult to state

definitely whether with the second group of substances formaldehyde is a direct product of photo-oxidation or is formed photochemically from carbon dioxide and water obtained during photo-oxidation of the organic substance.

We have shown that formaldehyde can be obtained from the photo-chemical reduction of carbon dioxide in aqueous solutions in the presence of photosensitisers. Moreover, formaldehyde is also produced in small amounts from aqueous solutions of potassium or sodium bicarbonate when exposed to light even without a photocatalyst. The reaction,

is highly endothermic and in the absence of an efficient photocatalyst it is difficult to obtain formaldehyde from the photochemical reduction of carbonic acid. Dilute solutions of alkali bicarbonate decompose according to the following equation

with liberation of small amounts of energy. In presence of light, this carbon dioxide may be slightly transformed into formaldehyde by the absorption of more energy. As the energy available from the decomposition of the bicarbonate is small, the amount of formaldehyde produced in this way is exceedingly small.

It is well known that practically all the organic compounds produce carbon dioxide and water when they are slowly oxidised and that this process is accompanied by the generation of energy. For instance, in the case of cane sugar and α -alanine, the following reaction may be supposed to take place

where E_s and E_a are the amounts of energy generated per g. mol. of cane sugar and α -alanine oxidised respectively. Since carbon dioxide, which is produced in these photo-oxidations is energy-rich, it should be more reactive than a molecule of ordinary carbon dioxide. A molecule of carbon dioxide, which is already in a reactive state, will require less energy to be activated in order to be reduced to formaldehyde than one of ordinary carbon dioxide. It will be interesting to note here that an active variety of carbon dioxide has recently been described by

Fowler (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1933, **A** 142, 362) in which an after-glow has also been observed.

In recent years, several authors notably Haber and Wausborough-Jones, (*Z physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **18B**, 103) have postulated that in many photochemical reactions taking place in aqueous solutions, the primary change is the photolysis of water molecules into H and OH. It appears that the photolysis of the activated water molecules into H and OH on the leaf surface due to the absorption of light by chlorophyll resembles the cases of photosensitised decomposition of water investigated *in vitro*. The hydrogen atoms so formed may reduce carbon dioxide and the OH radicals may unite to form hydrogen peroxide, which in its turn decomposes into water and oxygen with the liberation of energy as shown by Bonhoeffer and Pearson (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **14B**, 1)

This may be the probable mechanism of the evolution of oxygen during photosynthesis. The energy given out in the latter reaction may again be used.

Thus formaldehyde which is detected during the photo-oxidation of many organic substances is not always produced as a direct product of oxidation, but is usually obtained due to its photosynthesis from energy-rich carbon dioxide generated during oxidation. It may be mentioned here that we (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 567) have been able to obtain traces of formaldehyde from nascent carbon dioxide formed by the interaction of carbonates of barium and strontium with hydrochloric acid, in the absence of photocatalysts.

It will be interesting to note here that Lal (*Ann. Bot.*, 1934, **48**, 273) has observed the formation of alcohol and aldehydes during respiration of apples. These substances are supposed to be produced as a result of their photosynthesis from carbon dioxide generated during respiration in light. It seems probable, therefore, that the energy generated during the photo-oxidation of organic compounds supplies a part of the energy required for the photosynthesis of formaldehyde.

We are of the opinion that the production of formaldehyde from organic substances when exposed to air and light, which has been regarded as one of the drawbacks of the formaldehyde theory of photosynthesis, may not be quite correct. On the other hand, it is probably one of the strong arguments in favour of this view.

The view that formaldehyde detected in the photo-oxidation of substances of the third group, is produced as a result of its photosynthesis from energy rich carbon dioxide is supported by the following considerations.

(i) *Formaldehyde is detected in the photo-oxidation of numerous organic substances.* In the preceding pages, it has been shown that formaldehyde can be detected in the photo-oxidation of substances like oxalic acid, α -alanine, cane sugar, sodium oleate etc. This is not explicable from the view that it may be a direct product of the oxidation.

It is well known that carbon dioxide and water vapour are generally produced during the slow oxidation of organic compounds. The former at the moment of their generation are energy-rich and can readily produce formaldehyde photosynthetically. That is why formaldehyde has been detected in the photo-oxidation of organic substances.

(ii) *The ratio of the amount of organic substance photo-oxidised to that of formaldehyde formed is always very high.* Since the efficiency of the photosynthetic process that is, photosynthesis of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide and water is low, it is expected from the mechanism given here, that this ratio should be high. This has already been verified in the case of substances belonging to third group. Whenever formaldehyde is produced as a direct product of photo-oxidation of the organic substance, this ratio is about unity as shown with glycine, acetic acid, methyl violet etc. It will be interesting to note here that with potassium bicarbonate, the ratio of the amount of bicarbonate decomposed to that of formaldehyde formed is as high as 9800. This is because all the molecules of carbon dioxide produced during photo-oxidation or decomposition are not converted into formaldehyde.

(iii) *Temperature coefficient of the photoformation of formaldehyde from organic substance of the third group is less than unity above 30°.* An examination of the results summarised in Tables XII, XIII and XIV shows that the temperature coefficient of the production of formaldehyde from substances of the third group is less than unity above 30°, whilst with those of the first group it is more than unity. Moreover, the temperature coefficient of the photosynthesis of formaldehyde from potassium bicarbonate solutions is also comparable with the values obtained with substances of the third group. This is possibly due to the fact that above 30°, the loss of formaldehyde due to decomposition and evaporation becomes more potent than its photosynthesis with the net result that the yield of formaldehyde becomes less and less as the temperature increases. It should

be noted, however, that the percentage of the amount of the substance oxidised goes on increasing with temperature though the yield of formaldehyde follows the reverse order above 30°.

It will be interesting to note in this connection that the values for the temperature coefficient of photosynthesis as going on in the plants is less than unity above 30°. When substances like glycine, citric acid, etc. are oxidised at high temperatures, the yield of formaldehyde goes on increasing though not directly proportional to it, since it happens to be a product of their direct photo-oxidation. Thus from the study of the temperature coefficient also, it is concluded that the generation of formaldehyde from substances belonging to the third group is a photosynthetic process.

(iv) *The greater the energy generated in the photo-oxidation of a certain organic substance, the greater is the amount of formaldehyde detected during photo-oxidation.* If the view advanced here is correct, then the amount of formaldehyde photosynthetically formed during the photo-oxidation of a certain substance should depend upon the amount of energy evolved during oxidation, since this energy supplies a part of the energy needed for the photosynthesis of the former. This is evident from the results summarised in Table XVI. The amount of formaldehyde, when equivalent solutions of different substances are exposed to air and light, is greatest with salts of fatty acids, then follow the amino-acids and carbohydrates. However, with potassium bicarbonate it is much less. It is well known that the amount of heat generated per gramme of fat oxidised is 9 calories, whilst with both carbohydrates and proteins it is only 4.1 calories per gramme. It is clear, therefore, that the amount of formaldehyde formed during these photo-oxidations increases with the amount of the energy generated in the oxidation of organic substances. That is why the salts of the fatty acids, which are producers of large amount of energy, generate the maximum amount of formaldehyde, while potassium bicarbonate solutions give rise to amounts of formaldehyde which are comparable with the small amount of energy evolved during their decomposition. This is certainly due to the fact that the oxidation of organic matter in air and light sets free energy, and this energy of oxidation (respiration) is utilised in the photosynthesis of formaldehyde and other products. This experimental observation, therefore, is in favour of the view advanced here.

*Why Photosynthesis takes place in Red Light when it requires
a Radiation of 2552Å.*

It is generally believed that photosynthesis is most active in red and green lights. Wurmser (*Compt. rend.*, 1920, 171, 920) observed that

photosynthesis was most active in the red region, since the red rays were absorbed by chlorophyll to a greater extent than the blue or violet. These conclusions were corroborated by the researches of Warburg and Negelein (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 106, 191) on chlorella. Thermodynamically the reaction involved in carbon assimilation requires a wave-length of 2552 Å, but from the observations of Wurmser and Warburg it is clear that photosynthesis is most active in red light.

It is well known that even in the presence of light, respiration goes on along with photosynthesis in plants. It is probable that a part of the energy evolved during respiration already supplies a part of the energy needed for photosynthesis, thus rendering carbon assimilation possible by longer wave-length as reported by Wurmser and others. Hence apart from its activation by adsorption on chlorophyll surface, carbon dioxide used in photosynthesis may be partially activated by the energy of respiration.

These observations explain the difficulty of obtaining formaldehyde or carbohydrates from carbon dioxide *in vitro*, because the presence of an exothermal reaction, such as, the photo-oxidation of carbohydrates or other organic compounds seems to facilitate this reaction.

Why is Oxygen necessary in Photosynthesis ?

It is generally believed that photosynthesis going on in the plants stops in the complete absence of oxygen. Thus Boussingault ("*Agronomie Chimie Agricole et physiologie*", Paris, 1868, p. 329), Pringsheim (*Sitz. preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, 1887, p. 763), Willstätter and Stoll ("*Untersuchungen über die Assimilation*", Berlin, 1918, p. 349), Warburg (*Biochem. Z.*, 1919, 100, 230) and Spoehr and McGee (*Carnegie Inst. of Washington Publ.*, 1923, p. 325) have all shown that the plants lose their power of assimilation when kept in an oxygen-free atmosphere. It is rather striking that a substance which is produced in carbon assimilation should be indispensable to start it.

It has already been stated that photosynthesis in red light is possible only when a part of the energy required is supplied through respiration. In the absence of oxygen, respiration which supplies a part of the energy needed for photosynthesis will stop and hence the latter will also stop. When oxygen is present, respiration starts with the liberation of energy which is partially used up in photosynthesis. Thus oxygen is not directly used in photosynthesis, but influences it indirectly through respiration. Thus may be the probable explanation of the classical researches of Boussingault, Pringsheim, Willstätter and others. It appears, therefore,

that besides light, carbon dioxide, water and chlorophyll, energy from respiration and consequently oxygen are also necessary for photosynthesis.

Relation between Photosynthesis and Respiration.

Regarding the relation between photosynthesis and respiration, Spoehr and McGee ("Photosynthesis", 1926, p. 143) have stated as follows:—

"The light green varieties had a lower rate of respiration than the normal plants though there was no direct parallelism between chlorophyll content and respiration," and again "Respiration is an important internal factor affecting photosynthesis in addition to the chlorophyll content and the number of chloroplasts," and further "The exact manner in which these two processes may be linked is still an open question." Similar observations have been made by Miss Henrici (Inaugural Dissertation, Basel, 1918) and Boysen-Jensen (*Bot Tidsskrift*, 1916, 36, 319) who report that plants which have a high rate of photosynthesis have also a high velocity of respiration. However, the mechanism in which the two fundamental processes are related is not yet clearly understood.

From the viewpoint already discussed it will be evident that the greater the rate of respiration in a plant, the greater is the possibility of a supply of energy from it for photosynthesis. As already stated, photosynthesis appears to depend partly on the amount of energy produced during the photo-oxidation of organic substances, it is expected that the former will be related by respiration which is a constant source of supply of energy. Thus the way in which the two processes are connected seems to be the supply of energy evolved in respiration to be partially utilised in photosynthesis.

It will be interesting to note in this connection that Krebs and Henseleit (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1932, 210, 33) have reported that the formation of urea from ammonia and carbon dioxide in the animal body is closely related with respiration. According to Borsook and Keighley (*Science*, 1933, 77, 114), the synthesis of urea from ammonia and carbon dioxide by liver slices is associated with an increase of oxygen absorption.

It is well known that atmospheric nitrogen can only be fixed by some bacteria when supplied with energy from carbohydrates on their oxidation, or some other suitable oxidation reaction. It is of interest to note here that Dhar and Mukerji have recently observed the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in the soil when the latter is fed with molasses. They are of the opinion that the oxidation of the sugars present in the molasses induces the combination of atmospheric nitrogen and oxygen; the first reaction being the supplier of energy for the accomplishment of the latter. The amount of

nitrogen fixation in light is much greater than in the dark, because along with the oxidation energy of $(C_6H_{12}O_6 + 6O_2 = 6CO_2 + 6H_2O + 676 \text{ K. Cal})$ light is also utilised in the endothermal chemical change involved in nitrogen fixation $(N_2 + O_2 + 53.2 \text{ K. Cal} = 2NO)$.

In experiments *in vitro*, very little formaldehyde should be expected to be formed from carbonic acid or bicarbonate solutions on exposure to sunlight, because in sunlight short-wave ultraviolet rays exist in small amounts. On the other hand, in presence of ferrous and manganous salts we have been able to detect greater amounts of formaldehyde from carbonic acid than in their absence, because their oxidation in presence of air is an exothermal reaction which supplies a part of the energy needed for photosynthesis. Hence it is easier to obtain formaldehyde or any other energy-rich organic compound from carbonic acid or bicarbonate solutions on exposure to light when a suitable exothermal reaction is made to take place in the same system. In plants, such an exothermal reaction is respiration.

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